

DETERMINANTS OF DINING LOYALTY AMONG RESTAURANT GUESTS IN COTABATO CITY

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ABSTRACT

In an increasingly competitive restaurant industry, understanding factors influencing dining loyalty is essential for customer retention and long-term performance. While service quality has traditionally been emphasized as a key determinant, recent studies suggest that customer engagement and environmentally responsible practices may play a more prominent role in shaping repeat patronage. However, empirical evidence examining these determinants simultaneously within casual dining settings remains limited, especially in emerging urban contexts. This study aimed to examine the influence of service quality, with dimensions of reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, and tangibles; customer engagement, with dimensions of behavioral, emotional, and cognitive; and environmentally responsible practices on dining loyalty among customers of casual dining restaurants in Cotabato City. A descriptive-correlational research design was employed, with data from 195 patrons selected via random sampling using a validated survey questionnaire. Descriptive statistics assessed customer perceptions, while multiple regression identified significant predictors of loyalty. Results indicated that service quality, customer engagement, environmentally responsible practices, and loyalty were perceived at high levels. Regression analysis revealed that customer engagement and environmentally responsible practices significantly predicted loyalty, with engagement as the strongest predictor. Conversely, service quality did not demonstrate a significant direct effect on loyalty when analyzed alongside other variables, suggesting it functions as a basic expectation rather than a differentiating driver. The study contributes to hospitality management by emphasizing customer engagement and sustainability practices in strengthening loyalty within casual dining. It recommends restaurants prioritize enhancing emotional and behavioral engagement while integrating

environmentally responsible practices, and encourages future researchers to explore these relationships.

Keywords: *Casual dining, customer engagement, dining loyalty, environmentally responsible practices, service quality*

INTRODUCTION

Today, the hospitality industry has been recognized as one of the largest industries that supports the economic growth worldwide, where restaurants are a prime field that sets forth great deal of profit by satisfying customers through providing good food and memorable experiences, motivating diners to revisit and recommend to others (Dani et al., 2021). According to the National Restaurant Association (2025 State of the Restaurant Industry), the restaurant industry is braced to grow even more in 2025, with sales is expected to reach 1.5 trillion dollars and generate more than 200,000 net new jobs. In the Philippines, Filipino eating habits were reshaped due to rapid urban migration and increasing disposable income, resulting in economic growth and evolving consumption patterns (Laurent, 2026).

Despite of the numbers of growth and expansion, the restaurant industry face challenges in sustaining long-term operations in the existing competitive environment (Sormaz and Dursum, 2023). The first gap in this study is the service quality offered by the different casual dining restaurants in Cotabato City. According to the SERVPERF model by Cronin & Taylor (1992), service quality is evaluated based on the five dimensions; reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy and tangibles. Studies emphasized that customers' repeat visits are significantly influenced by remarkable service delivery (Uslu & Eren, 2020). However, ensuring consistently high service quality is difficult to sustain, and poor service experiences negatively affect restaurant reputation and customer retention (Daluz & Chavez, 2024). Another is customer engagement in restaurants in Cotabato City. Customer–brand relationships are interactive and experiential in nature (Hollebeek et al., 2011, 2014). Customer engagement directly impacts firm performance, behavioral intention, and word-of-mouth, driven by satisfaction, positive emotions, and trust (de Oliveira Santini et al., 2020). However, gaps remain due to negative customer engagement caused by perceived injustice and negative disconfirmation, which adversely affect customer behavior (Do & Robinson, 2020).

The third gap is in terms of environmentally responsible practices of the restaurant industry. The Green Restaurant Association (2021) defined these as sustainable food sourcing, use of eco-friendly materials, energy- and water-efficient operations, recycling and composting programs, and green facility design. However, with up to 26% of greenhouse emissions associated with restaurant food production and consumption, this leaves a substantial carbon footprint in the environment (Pei et al., 2022). According to Mai et al. (2023), challenges in fully implementing these practices include limited capital, lack of information, and insufficient research on consumer behavior toward green restaurant practices.

Overall, this study aligns with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by examining service quality, customer engagement, and environmentally responsible practices as predictors of dining loyalty. The findings will underscore how restaurants can foster profitability and sustainability through quality service delivery, stable employment opportunities, and improved economic growth, strengthening Cotabato City's reputation as a welcoming and sustainable community. Finally, insights from this research may encourage the community and the industry to promote responsible dining and consumption by valuing local products and minimizing waste (UNWTO, The Sustainable Development Goals Report, 2025).

Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

The study assumes that service quality, customer engagement, and environmentally responsible practices collectively influence guest loyalty in dining establishments. Anchored in the SERVPERF Model proposed by J. Joseph Cronin Jr. and Steven A. Taylor, service quality is conceptualized through reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, and tangibles, which shape customers' perceptions of service performance and contribute to satisfaction and loyalty formation. Empirical studies consistently demonstrate that well-delivered service experiences encourage repeat patronage and positive word-of-mouth behaviors in hospitality contexts (Ali et al., 2021; Eren et al., 2023; Faraj et al., 2021; Gitarisa & Dora, 2025; Zhong & Moon, 2020).

Complementing this perspective, customer engagement, grounded in Customer Engagement Theory advanced by Roderick J. Brodie and colleagues, captures the depth of customers' cognitive, emotional, and behavioral involvement with a restaurant. Cognitive engagement reflects customers' attention and evaluation of service experiences, emotional engagement represents affective attachment, and behavioral engagement manifests in participation, interaction, and advocacy. These dimensions jointly strengthen relational bonds with the establishment and are widely associated with stronger loyalty intentions (Huang & Chen, 2022; Islam, 2021; Rather et al., 2022; Shin & Back, 2020).

The framework further incorporates environmentally responsible practices, interpreted through the Stimulus–Organism–Response Model developed by Albert Mehrabian and James A. Russell, which posits that environmental stimuli—such as sustainable operations, waste reduction, and eco-friendly initiatives—shape customers' internal evaluations and subsequently influence behavioral responses such as loyalty and revisit intentions (Dhir et al., 2021; Khan & Alhumoudi, 2022; Mai et al., 2023).

These variables interact within a broader behavioral framework explained by the Theory of Planned Behavior proposed by Icek Ajzen, where attitudes toward the dining experience, perceived social expectations, and perceived control over dining choices influence intentions to return and recommend the establishment (Londoño et al., 2024; Purnami et al., 2025). Collectively, the interplay of high service performance, meaningful customer engagement, and visible environmental responsibility reinforces positive

attitudes and emotional attachment, thereby strengthening guests' behavioral intentions and sustaining dining loyalty in contemporary hospitality settings.

Research Questions

This study examined the shared influence of Service Quality and Customer Engagement as predictors of Dining Loyalty in Restaurants in Cotabato City. Specifically, it aimed to answer the following questions:

1. As assessed by the guests, what is the level of service quality in the dining restaurants in terms of:
 - 1.1. Reliability;
 - 1.2. Responsiveness;
 - 1.3. Assurance;
 - 1.4. Empathy;
 - 1.5. Tangibles?
2. What is the level of engagement among the guests of dining restaurants, considering their:
 - 2.1. Behavioral Engagement;
 - 2.2. Emotional Engagement;
 - 2.3. Cognitive Engagement?
3. What is the participants' assessment of the restaurants' environmentally responsible practices?
4. What is the level of loyalty among the guests in casual dining restaurants?
5. Do service quality, customer engagement, and environmentally responsible practices significantly predict dining loyalty?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive–correlational research design to examine whether service quality, customer engagement, and environmentally responsible practices predict dining loyalty in casual restaurants in Cotabato City. Service quality was operationalized through five dimensions—reliability, assurance, responsiveness, empathy, and tangibles—while customer engagement was measured through cognitive, emotional, and behavioral components. A total of 200 dining guests aged 18 years and above were selected through random sampling. The sample size satisfied methodological recommendations for multiple regression, which suggest at least 15–20 cases per predictor to ensure stable estimates (Green, 1991; Tabachnick & Fidell, 2019; Hair et al., 2019). Data were collected using adapted and previously validated instruments measuring service quality (Cronin & Taylor, 1992), customer engagement (Hollebeek et al., 2014), environmentally responsible practices (Han & Ryu, 2009; Pan & Ha, 2021; Ishaq, 2011), and dining loyalty (Ju & Chang, 2016; Jeong & Jang, 2010), all of which had established reliability and had undergone confirmatory factor analysis in prior studies. Descriptive statistics (frequency, percentage, and mean) were used to describe participants' assessments of service quality, customer engagement, environmentally

responsible practices, and dining loyalty. Multiple regression analysis was then applied to determine the predictive influence of the independent variables on dining loyalty after verifying key assumptions, including linearity, normality, homoscedasticity, and absence of multicollinearity.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Question 1. As assessed by the guests, what is the level of service quality in the dining restaurants in terms of:

- 1.1. Reliability**
- 1.2. Responsiveness**
- 1.3. Assurance**
- 1.4. Empathy**
- 1.5. Tangibles**

Table 1 presents participants' assessments of service quality across five dimensions, yielding an overall mean of 4.13 (SD = 0.55), interpreted as high, indicating consistently positive perceptions of service delivery in the surveyed restaurants. Among the dimensions, responsiveness (M = 4.15, SD = 0.60) and empathy (M = 4.15, SD = 0.63) obtained the highest ratings, suggesting that diners particularly value prompt service, staff attentiveness, and personalized assistance. These findings align with hospitality research emphasizing that timely responses and personalized interactions enhance customers' service experiences and satisfaction (Wirtz & Lovelock, 2021; Zeithaml et al., 2021). Reliability (M = 4.12, SD = 0.67) and tangibles (M = 4.14, SD = 0.64) were also rated high, reflecting positive perceptions of consistent service delivery and the physical aspects of the dining environment.

Table 1
Summary Table of Service Quality

Dimensions	Mean	Interpretation	SD
Reliability	4.12	High	0.67
Responsiveness	4.15	High	0.60
Assurance	4.09	High	0.65
Empathy	4.15	High	0.63
Tangibles	4.14	High	0.64
Service Quality	4.13	High	0.55

Assurance recorded the lowest mean (M = 4.09, SD = 0.65), although it remained within the high category, indicating slightly more varied perceptions regarding staff competence, professionalism, and ability to build customer trust. Previous studies highlight that employee product knowledge, clear communication, and adherence to hygiene standards contribute to customer confidence and perceived service reliability in restaurant settings (Ahmad et al., 2024; Bilqis et al., 2025). Overall, the results suggest that while all dimensions of service quality are positively perceived, responsiveness and

empathy play a particularly salient role in shaping favorable customer evaluations of restaurant service.

Research Question 2. What is the level of engagement among the guests of dining restaurants considering :

- 2.1. Behavioral Engagement**
- 2.2. Emotional Engagement**
- 2.3. Cognitive Engagement**

Table 2 presents the participants’ assessment of customer engagement across three dimensions, all of which were interpreted as “High,” with mean scores ranging from 4.12 to 4.20. This indicates that customers generally exhibit strong engagement with the restaurant. Among the dimensions, Emotional Engagement recorded the highest mean (M = 4.20, SD = 0.64), suggesting that participants feel a strong emotional connection with the restaurant. This is consistent with Barbosa et al. (2024), who found that “proactive engagement behaviors are encouraged by emotional attachment,” highlighting the importance of emotional connections in customer experiences. Similarly, Martin-Consuegra et al. (2021) confirmed that “the emotional components of customer experiences significantly relate to satisfaction loyalty.”

Table 2
Summary Table of Customer Engagement

Dimensions	Mean	Interpretation	SD
Behavioral	4.12	High	0.70
Emotional	4.20	High	0.64
Cognitive	4.12	High	0.73
Customer Engagement	4.15	High	0.60

Behavioral Engagement and Cognitive Engagement both obtained a mean score of 4.12, interpreted as “High,” indicating that participants are actively and mentally involved in their dining experiences. This finding is supported by Santoso and Agustini (2025), who identified “both behavioral and cognitive dimensions as critical components of customer engagement.” In addition, Chen et al. (2021) found that “customers’ behavioral actions and cognitive engagement are consistently linked to stronger engagement outcomes,” including revisit intentions and recommendations.

Research Question 3. What is the participants' assessment of the restaurants' environmentally responsible practices?

Table 3 presents the participants’ assessment of the restaurants’ environmentally responsible practices, with an overall mean of 4.12 (SD = 0.65), interpreted as “High,” indicating that sustainability efforts are generally recognized by customers. Among the indicators, “This restaurant is concerned about the preservation of the environment” obtained the highest mean (M = 4.24, SD = 0.78), suggesting that participants perceive the restaurants as genuinely committed to environmentally responsible practices. This is supported by Abdou et al. (2022), who noted that “consumers tend to associate green

actions with their own values, fostering emotional commitment and loyalty.” Similarly, Dhir et al. (2021) posited that “when customers perceive that restaurants are conscious with the environment and practice sustainability for green consumption, then the restaurants will gain repeat visits.”

Conversely, “This restaurant offers less meat and more vegetables, fruits, and vegetable protein” recorded the lowest mean ($M = 4.04$, $SD = 0.79$), although still interpreted as “Agree,” suggesting that customers may be less aware of plant-based menu initiatives. This aligns with Yang et al. (2025), whose findings show that “when restaurants have a greater availability of eco-friendly menu offering such as more protein and plant-based foods, this can positively influence customers’ consumption behaviors.” In addition, Jones et al. (2025) emphasized that “to reduce carbon foot prints and environmental impacts, chefs have been incorporating sustainable menu principles,” particularly by offering more plant-based and locally sourced produce.

Table 3
Frequency, Percentage, and Mean Distribution of the Participants' Assessment of the Restaurants' Environmentally Responsible Practices

Range	Description	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51-5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High	56	28.72
3.51-4.50	Agree	High	102	52.31
2.51-3.50	Neutral	Moderate	34	17.44
1.51-2.50	Disagree	Low	3	1.54
1.00-1.50	Strongly Disagree	Very Low	0	0.00
Total			195	100.0
Overall Mean				4.12
Interpretation				High
SD				0.65

Specific Indicators	M	Description	SD
1 This restaurant uses certified organic vegetables	4.10	Agree	0.86
2 This restaurant uses locally produced food products	4.11	Agree	0.89
3 This restaurant uses on-site food produce	4.06	Agree	0.93
4 This restaurant offers less meat and more vegetables, fruits, and vegetable protein	4.04	Agree	0.79
5 This restaurant has no disposable food service items (e.g. dishes and cups)	4.05	Agree	0.94
6 This restaurant uses disposable food service items for reusable or recycled materials	4.10	Agree	0.82
7 This restaurant uses take-out containers that are biodegradable or recyclable	4.21	Agree	0.87

- 8 This restaurant uses of low-flow toilets, flow restrictors on faucets, and water-less urinals in restrooms 4.11 Agree 0.78

Research Question 4. What is the level of loyalty among the guests in casual dining restaurants?

Table 4 presents the participants’ assessment of dining loyalty, with an overall mean of 4.16 (SD = 0.66), interpreted as “High,” indicating strong loyalty toward casual dining restaurants. Among the indicators, “I have said positive things about the company to other colleagues” recorded the highest mean (M = 4.34, SD = 0.72), highlighting advocacy as a key expression of loyalty. This is supported by the study of Jadmiko et al., 2025, whereas when customers are satisfied, customers share positive feedback which actually attracts new patrons through positive word-of-mouth. Similarly, Purnami and Nurcaya (2025) noted that “repeat visits and referrals reduce restaurants’ costs of acquiring new customers and thus increase their profitability.”

Conversely, “If the restaurant is not open yet, I’ll postpone the reservation to another day” obtained the lowest mean (M = 3.98, SD = 0.98), though still interpreted as “Agree,” suggesting variability in immediacy influenced by situational factors. This aligns with Le et al. (2024), who found that “utilitarian factors such as convenience and functional value indirectly affect revisit intentions.” In addition, Choi et al. (2025) emphasized that “place attachment can moderate revisit intentions,” indicating that loyalty behaviors may vary when situational barriers arise.

Table 4
Frequency, Percentage, and Mean Distribution of the Participants’ the Level of Loyalty Among the Guests in Casual Dining Restaurants

Range	Description	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51-5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High	74	37.95
3.51-4.50	Agree	High	89	45.64
2.51-3.50	Neutral	Moderate	30	15.38
1.51-2.50	Disagree	Low	2	1.03
1.00-1.50	Strongly Disagree	Very Low	0	0.00
Total			195	100.0
Overall Mean				4.16
Interpretation				High
SD				0.66

Specific Indicators	M	Description	SD
1 I would like to comeback to this restaurant in the future.	4.23	Agree	0.78
2 I would recommend this restaurant to my friends or others.	4.25	Agree	0.78
3 I am willing to spend more than I planned at this restaurant.	4.17	Agree	0.82

4	This is the only restaurant that I will visit.	4.03	Agree	0.97
5	If the restaurant is not open yet, I'll postpone the reservation to another day.	3.98	Agree	0.98
6	I consider the company as my first choice.	4.15	Agree	0.86
7	I have said positive things about the company to other colleagues.	4.34	Agree	0.72

Research Question 5. Do service quality, customer engagement, and environmentally responsible practices significantly predict dining loyalty?

Ho1: Service quality, customer engagement, and environmentally responsible practices do not significantly predict dining loyalty.

Ho2: Service quality does not significantly predict dining loyalty.

Ho3: Customer engagement does not significantly predict dining loyalty.

Ho4: Environmentally responsible practices do not significantly predict dining loyalty.

Table 5 shows that service quality, customer engagement, and environmentally responsible practices collectively and significantly predict dining loyalty ($F = 173.998$, $p < .001$), with a strong relationship ($R = 0.856$) and high explanatory power ($R^2 = 0.732$). This indicates that 73.2% of the variance in dining loyalty is explained by the three predictors, suggesting that relational and sustainability-related factors play a substantial role in shaping customers' loyalty toward restaurants. Consequently, Ho_1 is rejected. The remaining 26.8% of the variance may be attributed to other determinants not included in the model, such as food quality, price fairness, restaurant atmosphere, brand image, and customer satisfaction, which have been identified in hospitality research as important drivers of loyalty behavior (Han et al., 2020; Rather et al., 2021).

Examining the predictors individually, service quality did not significantly influence dining loyalty ($\beta = .029$, $t = 0.426$, $p = .670$); therefore, Ho_2 cannot be rejected. This suggests that while diners generally perceive service quality positively, it may function as a basic expectation or hygiene factor rather than a decisive determinant of loyalty. In contemporary restaurant contexts, customers may assume a certain level of acceptable service and instead base loyalty decisions on experiential and relational aspects of the dining encounter (Hidayat et al., 2020; Rather & Hollebeek, 2023). In contrast, customer engagement emerged as the strongest predictor of dining loyalty ($\beta = .644$, $B = .700$, $t = 9.068$, $p < .001$), indicating that higher levels of cognitive, emotional, and behavioral engagement substantially enhance customers' intention to revisit and recommend the restaurant. Thus, Ho_3 is rejected, supporting studies that emphasize the importance of interactive and relationship-driven experiences in hospitality settings (Hollebeek & Macky, 2023; Brodie et al., 2019). Similarly, environmentally responsible practices significantly predicted dining loyalty ($\beta = .234$, $B = .237$, $t = 4.105$, $p < .001$), leading to the rejection of Ho_4 . This finding suggests that visible sustainability initiatives strengthen customer trust and ethical alignment with the restaurant, thereby encouraging repeat patronage and positive advocacy (Dhir et al., 2021). Overall, the results highlight that while service

quality remains a necessary operational standard, customer engagement and environmental responsibility are more salient drivers of dining loyalty.

Table 5
Regression Analysis on the Influence of Service Quality, Customer Engagement, and Environmentally Responsible Practices on Dining Loyalty

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
(Constant)	.144	.190		0.756	.450
Service quality	.034	.080	.029	0.426	.670
Customer Engagement	.700	.077	.644	9.068**	.000
Environmental practices	.237	.058	.234	4.105**	.000

Model Summary

R = 0.856	R ² = 0.732	Adj. R ² = 0.728	F = 173.998**	p = .000
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**significant at 0.01 level

Conclusions

The study provides an integrated examination of service quality, customer engagement, and environmentally responsible practices in explaining dining loyalty among casual restaurant patrons in Cotabato City. Anchored in the SERVPERF Model of J. Joseph Cronin Jr. and Steven A. Taylor, service quality remains a fundamental operational component of the dining experience, particularly through responsiveness and empathy, which reflect diners' expectations for prompt service and personalized attention. Customer engagement, interpreted through Customer Engagement Theory advanced by Roderick J. Brodie and colleagues, demonstrates the importance of cognitive involvement, emotional connection, and behavioral participation in strengthening customers' relationships with restaurants. In addition, environmentally responsible practices influence dining loyalty in ways consistent with the Stimulus–Organism–Response Model of Albert Mehrabian and James A. Russell, suggesting that sustainability-related initiatives shape customer perceptions and behavioral responses. Interpreted through the Theory of Planned Behavior proposed by Icek Ajzen, service quality appears to function primarily as a baseline expectation, whereas relational experiences and value-oriented practices—particularly engagement and sustainability—play a more salient role in shaping dining loyalty.

Two major limitations should be considered. First, the study was limited to diners from selected casual restaurants in Cotabato City, which may restrict the generalizability of the results to other geographic contexts or restaurant categories. Second, the cross-sectional research design captures customer perceptions at a single point in time and therefore cannot account for possible changes in loyalty behavior over time. Despite these constraints, the study contributes to hospitality research by integrating service quality, customer engagement, and environmentally responsible practices within a single predictive framework in a local Philippine dining context, offering empirical insight into

how relational and sustainability-oriented factors operate alongside traditional service constructs in influencing restaurant loyalty.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are proposed.

1. **Restaurant Owners and Management** may prioritize emotional customer engagement through personalized services, loyalty programs, and interactive communication, while strengthening visible and authentic environmentally responsible practices. The Management may proactively build stronger and long-term customer relationships by encouraging feedback and maintaining follow-ups, recognizing loyal patrons, and creating a loyalty program. Continuous staff training in product knowledge, professionalism, and confident service delivery is recommended to improve assurance.

2. **Restaurant Staff and Front-line Employees** may undergo continuous training and coaching to enhance menu knowledge, confidence, and professionalism in handling customer interactions.

3. **Hospitality Education Administrators** may integrate customer engagement and environmentally responsible practices into curricula and training programs, emphasizing experiential service delivery and sustainability as key drivers of dining loyalty, while reinforcing service quality as a baseline competency.

4. **Hospitality Management Faculty** may integrate curriculum and classroom activities that emphasize the importance of customer engagement and environmentally responsible practices in fostering dining loyalty, while reinforcing service quality as a foundational skill and baseline customer expectation. In kitchen laboratories, environmentally responsible practices can be applied through food waste reduction, proper recycling and composting, use of energy-efficient equipment, sustainable sourcing, and menu planning that emphasizes more vegetable-based dishes and reduced meat usage.

5. **Future Researchers** may explore additional predictors of dining loyalty, expand the study scope across restaurant types and locations, and employ qualitative methods to deepen understanding of customers' emotional and cognitive engagement.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Prior to data collection, the researcher implemented established ethical research protocols, including securing informed consent, ensuring voluntary participation, and protecting the confidentiality of participants' responses. The conduct of the study was guided by the ethical principles of respect for persons, beneficence, and justice, as outlined in The Belmont Report issued by the National Commission for the Protection of Human Subjects of Biomedical and Behavioral Research (1979). Participants were

provided with clear and sufficient information regarding the purpose of the study, the procedures involved, and their rights as participants. They were informed that participation was entirely voluntary and that they could withdraw from the study at any point without penalty. The principle of beneficence was applied by minimizing potential risks and ensuring that the study posed no physical, psychological, or social harm to participants. Data collection procedures were non-invasive and conducted in ways that respected participants' comfort and privacy. Confidentiality was maintained by excluding personally identifiable information and securing all data for academic use only. The principle of justice was observed through fair and appropriate participant selection procedures, ensuring that participants were included based on clearly defined criteria and that no group was unfairly burdened or excluded from the research. These ethical safeguards collectively ensured the protection, dignity, and well-being of participants throughout the study.

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